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Preregistration on zenodo.org

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Preregistration: Investigating the temporal dynamics of Type-A and Type-B metacontrast masking functions

General approach

We report how we determined our sample size, all data exclusions (if any), all manipulations, and all measures in the study (“21-word solution”). We do not report conditions, variables, analyses, or participants selectively without transparently revealing the reasoning behind the selection. We avoid the use of analysis techniques with excessive and unwarranted user-degrees of freedom. In our style of experimentation, we subscribe to the psychophysical tradition of “small- N / large- N_i designs” (Smith & Little, 2018) that relies on the careful analysis of individual observers instead of extensive averaging across many observers. We therefore prefer to draw statistical power from a large number of trial repetitions rather than the number of participants (Arend & Schäfer, 2019; Baker et al., 2020). We follow the principle that research articles must be methodologically transparent without requiring additional knowledge of supplementary materials or preregistration documents. We share data with natural persons for scientific purposes in accordance with German data protection laws (Landesdatenschutzgesetz Rheinland-Pfalz).

Novel or preexisting data?

No data have been collected for this study yet.

Purpose of the experiment, major hypotheses and expectations

We measure masking effects in error rates. On each trial, participants are presented with a brief target display (square or diamond) followed by a mask display (disc with a central cutout corresponding to the superposition of the square and diamond targets). Participants are instructed to discriminate the target stimulus as accurately as possible by pressing one of two response keys. The target-mask SOA is varied in five steps (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 ms). Two variations are employed. In Variation 1, luminance levels decrease in the order of presentation (background > target > mask); In Variation 2, luminance increases from the background to the target stimulus, followed by a mask that is darker than the background.

We measure full masking functions of target discrimination accuracy as a function of SOA. Our hypothesis is that the luminance variation in Variation 1 should lead to Type-A masking functions (target discriminability increases linearly with SOA), while the variation in Variation 2 should result in Type-B masking functions (U-shaped function of target discriminability and SOA).

We further apply hazard analysis and conditional accuracy functions to investigate the time course of visual masking. This analysis is explorative. However, we generally expect higher accuracy at fast compared to slow responses.

Design, independent variables, and dependent variables; variables that are not part of the analysis plan

We apply a completely crossed two-factorial repeated-measures design with factors of SOA (5 levels) and luminance variation (2 levels). Each participant participates in every condition over a course of four sessions (two sessions of one variant, followed by two

sessions of the other variant, counterbalanced across participants). All analyses follow this same factorial structure.

The dependent variable is accuracy. Apart from the mean accuracy, we apply hazard analysis and conditional accuracy functions where physical time is subdivided into time bins and the hazard rate of responding as well as accuracy of responses are plotted as a function of time (see our tutorial paper by Panis, F. Schmidt, Wolkersdorfer, & Schmidt, 2020). There are no further dependent variables.

Apart from the major independent variables, there is an additional variable that is needed for counterbalancing purposes and the avoidance of experimental artifacts. This is the concrete target identity (square or diamond). This balancing variable is not part of the analysis plan and is averaged across. The same holds for all participant variables, like gender, age, handedness, or other characteristics.

Criteria for data trimming, discarding of data or participants, or selective analyses

We rarely have to exclude participants from analysis after data are collected. We only do so if a participant clearly does not follow instructions. An indicator of that could be monotonic use of the same response key. Apart from that, sometimes participants' data cannot be used because of equipment malfunction, mistaken instructions, or other unforeseen events. In such cases, we try to recover as much of the valid data as we can. However, when a participant decides to abort an experiment prematurely we discard all data from that person. Finally, we exclude trials with problems in experimental timing, such as skipped monitor frames as measured by the timing feedback from the Psychophysics Toolbox.

A frequently used strategy for data analysis in unconscious perception research is to selectively analyze trials or participants with certain performance outcomes (e.g., trials with low visibility ratings or participants not exceeding certain target discrimination

criteria). We are strongly opposed to such practices, which lead to strong statistical distortions and artifacts like regression to the mean, and we never use them.

Planned analyses, variable transformations

The major analysis strictly follows the two-factorial structure of the independent variables. We apply two-factorial repeated-measures analysis of variances (ANOVA; factors SOA, and luminance variation) on accuracy. Practice blocks are discarded. Accuracies p are transformed into logits according to the formula $\text{logit} = \log [p/(1-p)]$, after replacing perfect accuracies of 0 and 1 with values of $1/2r$ and $1 - 1/2r$, where r is the number of stimulus repetitions per participant. In other words, half of a response is added to or subtracted from any perfect score to prevent division by zero.

Statistical decision criteria and multiple tests

We generally report statistical tests as conventionally significant at a false-positive risk of $\alpha = .05$ because many readers use that criterion. However, internally we are more conservative and regard p -values between .01 and .05 as only mild evidence against the null hypothesis and would not base strong conclusions on such results. Greenhouse-Geisser correction is used for all tests irrespective of the outcome of a formal sphericity test.

Corrections for type-I error accumulation are handled in the following way. We follow the custom of not correcting the set of F tests within a single ANOVA model for multiple tests (usually three main effects and four interactions). We also follow the custom of not correcting F tests across the ANOVAS of different dependent variables. However, when we conduct k multiple tests *within* the frame of an analysis (e.g., analyzing priming effects separately for each SOA), we use a Bonferroni correction of $\alpha' = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k$.

Foreseeable follow-up analyses

In many experiments, discoveries in the data lead to follow-up analyses. Furthermore, reviewers often request additional analyses. Examples would be learning effects (time-courses of effects across blocks or sessions), sequential effects (e.g., response times following error trials), or delta plots. We always clearly specify which analyses are planned (follow from the design) and which ones are post-hoc (based on discoveries).

Not every aspect of data analysis can be preplanned. For instance, it is always an executive decision to choose a good bin size for a histogram, a color code for a heat-map, or the minimum number of trials that allow for plotting a data point in a conditional-accuracy or hazard diagram. Unexpected problems may lead to unbalanced designs or unusual distributions of data, forcing analyzers to adjust statistical methods. Advances in methodological knowledge and creative development of methods may even lead to the replacement of one technique by a superior one. We believe that this is generally a sign of scientific progress, not of researcher degrees of freedom running wild. We are transparent about such issues and developments in our own analysis strategies and clearly identify them in our publications.

Sample size determination

In multi-factor repeated-measures designs, statistical power can be calculated if all effect sizes can be predicted along with their respective error variances. In practice, however, too many terms are unknown for a meaningful power analysis. Because the number of trials per participant and condition is about as important for power as the number of participants (Arend & Schäfer, 2019; Baker et al., 2020; Smith & Little, 2018), we control *measurement precision* at the level of individual participants in single tasks and stimulus conditions (Biafora & Schmidt, 2019; Lakens, 2022). For each task, we calculate precision as s/\sqrt{r} (Eisenhart, 1962), where s is a single participant's standard deviation in a given cell of the basic design (e.g., SOA x luminance variation) and r is the number of repeated measures in each cell and subject. We assume standard deviations of $SD = 60$ ms for

response times (based on our own benchmark data) and the maximal possible standard deviation of .5 for error and accuracy rates. For instance, when $r = 100$, we can expect a precision of $60/\sqrt{100} = 6$ ms in individual response times and $0.5/\sqrt{100} = 0.05$ (five percentage points) in error/accuracy rates. This means that an uncorrected 95% confidence interval calculated within a single observer would be able to resolve mean differences of two precision units, $\approx 2s/\sqrt{r}$.

In the present experiment, $r = 400$, and we assume max. $SD(\text{Accuracy}) = 0.5$. Therefore, we expect a precision of 2.5 percentage points in accuracy scores of each individual observer and condition. Precision thus exceeds our previous recommendations for response priming studies ($r = 60$, F. Schmidt et al., 2011).

Based on these considerations, we measure 10 observers in all experimental conditions and 400 trials per condition and observer. In our publications we show the data patterns of all individual observers.

Literature:

- Arend, M. G., & Schäfer, T. (2019). Statistical power in two-level models: A tutorial based on Monte Carlo simulation. *Psychological Methods, 24*(1), 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000195>
- Baker, D. H., Vilidaite, G., Lygo, F. A., Smith, A. K., Flack, T. R., Gouws, A. D., & Andrews, T. J. (2020). *Power contours: Optimising sample size and precision in experimental psychology and human neuroscience*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/met0000337>
- Biafora, M., & Schmidt, T. (2019). Induced dissociations: Opposite time courses of priming and masking induced by custom-made mask-contrast functions. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics, 82*, 1333–1354.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-019-01822-4>
- Eisenhart, C. (1962). Realistic evaluation of the precision and accuracy of instrument calibration systems. In H. H. Ku (Ed.), *Precision Measurement and Calibration (1969)*, (pp. 21–48). Washington, D.C.: National Bureau of Standards.
- Lakens, D. (2022). Sample size justification. *Collabra: Psychology, 8*(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.33267>

Panis, S., Schmidt, F., Wolkersdorfer, M. P., & Schmidt, T. (2020). Analyzing response times and other types of time-to-event data using event history analysis: A tool for mental chronometry and cognitive psychophysiology. *I-Perception, 11*, 1-24. doi: 10.1177/2041669520978673

Schmidt, F., Haberkamp, A., & Schmidt, T. (2011). Dos and don'ts in response priming research. *Advances in Cognitive Psychology, 7*, 120-131. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10053-008-0092-2>

Smith, P. L., & Little, D. R. (2018). Small is beautiful: In defense of the small-N design. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review, 25*(6), 2083-2101. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-018-1451-8>